

**Representations of War and Resistance in Khaled Hosseini's
A Thousand Splendid Suns and Markus Zusak's *The Book Thief*:**

A Comparative Postcolonial Study

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Abstract

This research paper presents a comparative analysis of war and resistance in Khaled Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns* (2007) and Markus Zusak's *The Book Thief* (2005), focusing on how war and oppression shape human identity, memory, and resistance. Through the lens of postcolonial theory, the study shows how the characters experience othering, displacement, subjectivity, and hybridity as a result of political conflict and historical trauma. This study aims to explore how colonized individuals use quiet resistance not only as a means of survival, but also to express their sense of identity and inner self. Both authors present deeply human responses to violence, particularly through the voices of marginalized characters—Laila and Mariam in Afghanistan, and Liesel in Nazi Germany. The paper argues that these texts challenge dominant historical narratives by centering the experiences of women and children. The paper has reached four findings. (1) Personal memory, knowledge, and voice can be a form of resistance. (2) Although these characters are shaped by oppression and violence, manage to reclaim their subjectivity through the power of storytelling, love, sacrifice, and defiance. (3) Characters' resistance is embodied through small, quiet acts of rebellion that challenge colonial, patriarchal, and oppressive forces. (4) War does not just affect childhood memory; instead, it goes beyond that.

Keywords: Afghanistan, *Book Thief*, Nazi Germany, postcolonial theory, resistance, *Thousand Splendid Suns*, Taliban, war, World War II

Khaled Hosseini (1965-) is an Afghan-American physician and novelist. A contemporary writer who is widely known for his novels that highlight life in Afghanistan, particularly suffering and resilience of its people during decades of war. Hosseini's first novel, *The Kite Runner* (2003) was a critical and commercial success and his second novel, *A Thousand Splendid Suns* (2007), is one of his most important works that highlights the struggles of Afghani women, a novel set in Afghanistan during civil war and Taliban rule, he tells a story of two Afghani women Mariam and Laila, who endure abuse, loss, and social oppression. Hosseini's novels have spread awareness about Afghanistan's people and culture. Markus Zusak (1975-) is an Australian-German writer. Also, a contemporary writer known for his distinctive narrative style and his ability to describe human suffering and historical issues. Zusak wrote many international novels, the most important of which is his fourth novel, *The Messenger* (2002) and his fifth novel, *The Book Thief* (2005), a novel set in Nazi Germany during WWII that explores the horrors of war through the eyes of young girl named Liesel. Despite their different cultural backgrounds, both authors using war as a backdrop to explore identity, memory, and resistance. Using marginalized voices to depict the psychological and emotional impact of war on ordinary people, especially women and children.

Since no one has addressed this study before, this research paper will discuss a comparative linear study of these topics, Hosseini's *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and Zusak's *The Book Thief* through the concept of resistance during war, which will be discussed in this study. However, this study leads to answering a central question: How can war be overcome through resistance? Answering this question contributes to answering other related ones: (1) How can memory, knowledge, and voice be a form of resistance? (2) How characters' identities be shaped through the use of storytelling, love, and sacrifice as tools of resistance? (3) What kinds of challenges can lead the characters to embody and express resistance? (4) Does war only affect childhood memory?

Through the lens of Postcolonial theory this study will examine the cultural, political, and psychological effects of colonialism and its aftermath, with a particular focus on how the effects of colonial power continue to affect formerly colonized societies. According to Ashcroft, postcolonialism is: "the discourse that interrogates colonial domination and its enduring consequences" (2). This study uses postcolonial theory to analyze how war and resistance are portrayed in *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and *The Book Thief* through key concepts such as identity and subjectivity, othering, displacement, oppression, cultural hybridity, and resistance. For example, the experience of displacement as a result of war in both novels reflects what Said described as: "the unhealable rift forced between a human being and a native place" (173). Characters such as Laila and Liesel are shaped by environments that destabilize them, pushing them into a state of resistance and defiance. Cultural hybridity, as Bhabha defines it: "in the contact zones where cultures meet and redefine themselves" (55), and is evident in the formation of Liesel's German identity through her relationships with Jewish characters. Moreover, acts of resistance through love, reading, and sacrifice reflect what Elleke Boehmer has described as: "the everyday subversion of oppressive systems through the reclaiming of personal agency" (119). This is discussed from the perspective that resistance consists of many actions that even war cannot stop.

The concept of othering used by dominant powers to dehumanize and marginalize the oppressed. Edward Said defines "othering" as the process of portraying the colonized as: "not only different, but inferior" (93). In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, women like Mariam and Laila are treated as "other" within a patriarchal society that works to silence and control them. Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, Max, as a Jew under the Nazi regime, becomes the ultimate other, hunted and erased from society's accepted norms. These experiences deeply influence the characters' identity and subjectivity. As Homi Bhabha explains, identity: "never unified but always in process, constantly negotiated in the context of cultural conflict"(56). Mariam's identity evolves from shame to dignity through her resistance. Liesel's self is gradually shaped as she

discovers the power of words as a tool for defining herself beyond fear and Nazi propaganda.

Ultimately, resistance becomes a tool through which characters reclaim their voice and agency. Elleke Boehmer notes that resistance in postcolonial literature: "is not only political but deeply personal, embedded in everyday acts of survival" (121). From Mariam's sacrifice at the end of the novel to Liesel's defiance of the system through stories, both novels portray resistance as an act of reclaiming humanity in the face of attempts at erasure. In postcolonial literature, memory is a key tool for understanding how history and characters are reconstructed, and how individuals and communities can reinterpret their pasts of suffering and oppression. Memory reveals the ways in which individuals choose to engage with the past, whether through resistance or reconstruction, and highlights how personal and collective history shapes identity. Childhood is also depicted as a stage of development, but at the same time, it is often marked by tragedy and devastation due to colonial conflicts or wars. Childhood is often used as a symbol of the loss of innocence due to the effects of discrimination and violence. These postcolonial elements not only reveal the characters' internal struggles, but also reveal how war reinforces systems of domination, and how resistance can become a means of rebuilding identity and healing.

Highlighting the historical and political contexts in both novels shows that how postcolonial affect and shape the lives of ordinary people. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Hosseini explains how Afghanistan has suffered from numerous foreign interventions, beginning with the Soviet invasion that supported the communist government against "Mujahideen," leading to widespread destruction and instability. After the Soviet withdrawal, "Mujahideen" factions turned against each other, leading to a civil war. The country was plunged into chaos, and Kabul was under bombardment, as shown in the novel: "Late in the afternoon, the shells began to fall on Kabul like heavy snow, bringing with them dust and mud that scattered everywhere" (Hosseini 116), also: "As the planes bombed Kabul, the ground shook beneath our feet, and the sound of explosions filled the air like thunder" (Hosseini 175). Likewise, in *The Book*

Thief, Zusak explains how Nazi Germany demonstrated its power and control during World War II, using oppression, fear, and intimidation. This is represented through the novel: "The air was thick with smoke, and the flames that were running along the ground could be heard. The roar of the bombs was like a hundred lions, all of them roaring at once" (Zusak 156). Zusak uses this description to illustrate the devastation left behind by the occupation and how the bombing of cities was a part of daily life during this period. In both novels, colonialism was like a monster devouring its prey. It affects lives, minds, thoughts, and identities of individuals, and even after it ended, it left behind a lot of fear, pain, and wounds that can never be healed.

War in both novels is not only about the battles, but also, about the deep emotional and psychological suffering endured by individuals, especially women and children. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, suffering was not limited on the war only, despite the Soviet invasion, civil war, and Taliban regime, Afghani women suffered from male oppression. Hosseini represents this through Mariam and Laila, who both suffered from the violence outside and the abuse inside their home: "In times of war, no one escapes suffering, whether man or woman. But the women of Afghanistan suffer more, bearing the weight of customs and traditions that restrict them" (203). Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, the sound of bombs is still ringing everywhere in Germany, in addition to the shortage of food and the specter of death that has loomed over the city and has become a normal daily occurrence, and with the increase in persecution against the Jews and chasing them everywhere to kill them, through the eyes of Liesel, it depicts how the war takes away the people she loves and it shows that through the novel that war destroys families, homes, and innocence: "The last time I saw her was red. The sky was like soup, boiling and stirring. In some places it was burned. There were black crumbs, and pepper, streaked across the redness" (Zusak 497). Describing the sky after the bombing and the death of her foster family and her friend Rudy, she was the only one left. This quote shows how much Liesel suffered because of her loss. In both novels, all that war meant to Mariam, Laila, and Liesel was loss despite the differences in what

they lost, whether it was identity, dignity, or even people they loved, facing this at a young age left them with a lot of wounds and pain.

The role of women and their resistance is often marginalized because it is believed that war is solely a masculine domain, but in fact, women face many challenges during wars and colonialism. Both novels subvert this by foregrounding female perspectives. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, resistance in general and women in particular are shown. Hosseini explores this through Mariam and Laila, who resisted not only colonialism but also the traditions of society and the control imposed by the Taliban. Women were stripped of their rights to education and life, even to choose the person they wanted. Mariam and Laila's resistance was represented by defending each other. Although they did not directly participate in the war, their steadfastness in the face of destruction and bombing was resistance in itself. After a life of being silenced and mistreated, Mariam performs the ultimate act of resistance when she kills Rasheed, her husband, to save Laila: "She would never leave her mark on Mammy and Babi's doorframe, never peer at herself in a mirror in Laila's house, and never again see Zalmai's hair light up in the sun. But as she walked away from the house, she felt peace. She was leaving the world as a woman who had loved and been loved back" (Hosseini 329). This act was not only to protect her friend, but also a refusal to surrender to the injustice represented by war and male violence. She sacrifices her life not out of despair, but out of love and strength. Compared with *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, *The Book Thief's* resistance was represented by words, and Liesel's love of reading books that becomes her weapon. Although the war had caused her to lose so much, books were her only cure. Reading during the bombing became a form of comfort and survival: "The words. Why did they have to exist? Without them, there wouldn't be any of this. Without words, the Führer was nothing" (Zusak 521). Liesel realized that the words Hitler used to control them could be a means of resistance against his Nazi campaign. Reading aloud to others was an act of resistance, defiance, and steadfastness.

Through the lens of gendered resistance, both novels highlight how female characters resisted a system of oppression not with force, but through love, sacrifice,

courage, and knowledge. In doing so, the concept of resistance is defined not only as a means of defense and survival, but also as a means of will, strength, and resilience. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, the Taliban's rule is both political and patriarchal, restricting women's movement, education, and autonomy. Despite all that Mariam and Laila have suffered, they have not lost their determination and have not given up on their children, their love, and their defense of each other. Likewise, in *The Book Thief*, Liesel resists the Nazi regime's control over identity and truth, particularly as a little girl. Though less overtly gendered than Mariam and Laila, her actions still reflect subtle feminist resistance to systems of dominance. In both novels, resistance is not violent, but rather quiet, deeply human, and personal, manifested in their lives and daily stances against the war. From this, Postcolonial feminism explores how gender intersects with historical, cultural, and political oppression. While Mariam and Laila are symbols of women's resistance, Liesel's growth and strength through books and emotional resilience, both represent women's survival in patriarchal-dominated societies.

Knowledge and education have a significant impact on the characters' identity, their resilience, and their sense of control and self-worth in a world that constantly threatens to erase them. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, however, Mariam, who cannot get an education, despite begging her mother to let her go to school, her mother responds harshly: "What's the sense schooling a girl like you? It's like shining a spittoon" (Hosseini 18). Laila relates to education and school, and it has become a way for her to escape her reality and understand the world. Despite the suffering of Afghan women, Laila's father encourages her to complete her education, he tells her: "Marriage can wait, education cannot" (Hosseini 103). This statement not only reveals his progressive mindset but also positions education as a form of empowerment for Laila. However, later in the novel, showing that knowledge and learning—whether formal or informal—can still transform lives. Thus, education in the novel is both a privilege and a battleground, particularly for women struggling against patriarchal and political forces. Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, education and reading become central to Liesel's emotional survival and quiet resistance against the horrors of Nazi Germany. Liesel

begins learning to read with her foster father, Hans, and this process becomes a source of empowerment. Liesel's literary growth helps her better understand the world as she finds comfort in books in a world filled with chaos. Her act of writing her own story at the end becomes an ultimate form of resistance: "She wrote her story in the basement, in the air raid shelter" (Zusak 528). In a world dominated by propaganda and violence, words are Liesel's only means of survival and resistance. During a book burning, Liesel sneaks into the fire to steal a book about to catch fire and hides it in her jacket. Although the dust from the burning nearly suffocates her, she takes it home and does not let go. In both novels, education and knowledge are central to characters' development, and their sacrifices for knowledge and learning are another form of resistance.

War directly affects the childhood of characters and their identity. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Laila loses her childhood when war destroys her home and kills her family, forcing her to marry Rasheed at a young age: "The past held only this wisdom: that love was a damaging mistake, and its accomplice, hope, a treacherous illusion" (Hosseini 194). Despite the depth of this sentence, it shows how the war and personal losses deeply affect Laila's emotional state, shaping her resilience and caused her to lose the innocence of childhood and the simple sense of love and security. Meanwhile, at the beginning of her life Mariam is faced the reality of being an illegitimate child and is labeled a "harami" then her mother's death and her marriage to Rasheed at a young age deeply affects her, but she did not lose her faith and hope in life. Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, Liesel witnesses executions, destruction, and the passing of those she loves. Her childhood begins with her brother's funeral: "The brother shivers. The sister moans. In the arms of the mother, the girl shivers and moans simultaneously. And then, they're all there together, on a train, and then the boy is dead" (Zusak 19). This event marks a major turning point in her life and reveals the cruelty of war and early death. Both *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and *The Book Thief* depict war not only as a destructive force, but also as a catalyst that shapes the characters' identities and decisions. Also, both novels explore how war strips away childhood innocence but also fosters unexpected resilience. Both *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and *The Book Thief*

illustrate how identity is not fixed, but constantly reshaped by trauma, resistance, and emotional bonds, making subjectivity a site of both vulnerability and power.

The relationships formed during childhood become vital sources of strength and resistance for all characters. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, after the shock of losing her family and everything she knew, Laila finds comfort and friendship with Mariam. Despite its violent beginnings, it develops into a form of resistant love, defining their identity and their resistance against the war and Rasheed. The innocence of childhood is also represented by Laila's son, Zalmai. Despite the harshness of the world, Laila works to protect and educate him. However, the war had a profound impact on his personality: "Zalmai was two and a half. He had his father's hairline, his mother's mouth, and his father's eyes. He was quick with a laugh and easily angered. He was a clingy child who cried when Mariam left for the bathhouse" (Hosseini 274). This description shows that Zalmai is a young child at the age of innocence, but he grew up in an atmosphere charged with violence and tension, which affected his emotional behavior. Likewise, in *The Book Thief*, Liesel finds security and guidance in her foster parents in the absence of her biological parents. Liesel copes with emotional pain through writing, but she remains affected by memories of war and death. Hans's love for Liesel, her friendship with Max, and her love for Rudy are all manifestations of human care amidst chaos. But as always, it does not last long once again, Liesel loses everything: "The bombing of Himmel Street was the last thing everyone expected. As always, it was the unexpected that ruined everything. It brought the end. It killed everyone but her" (Zusak 497). In this shocking scene, Liesel loses everyone she loves to the bombing. Despite her young age, she experiences a profound loss that ends what remains of her childhood. War here does not just destroy buildings, it also deprives children of their innocence, security, and loved ones. Both novels portray how war leaves deep psychological scars on children, while also showing their remarkable capacity to endure and adapt.

Using storytelling to give a voice to marginalized characters, challenging dominant historical narratives that often silence them. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, Hosseini

centers the voices of Afghani women, Through Mariam's internal thoughts and Laila's determination, the novel reclaims the narrative of women living under war, patriarchy, and oppression. Rather than portraying them as mere victims, Hosseini shows them as complex individuals with emotions, agency, and strength. Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, Zusak chooses Death as a narrator to highlight the forgotten stories of innocent Germans and Jews during World War II. Characters like Liesel and Max, who would usually be invisible in official histories, are given powerful voices. Max, a Jewish man in hiding, writes stories over the pages of *Mein Kampf*—autobiographical manifesto by the Nazi Party leader Adolf Hitler—symbolically reclaiming the narrative from Nazi ideology. Through these narrative choices, both novels illustrate how representation and voice can act as powerful tools of resistance against silencing, injustice, and historical erasure. Oppressive regimes in both novels—whether the Taliban in Afghanistan or the Nazis in Germany—limit personal freedom and silence dissent, especially for marginalized individuals. Storytelling, reading, and writing function as tools of empowerment and resistance in both novels, helping characters reclaim agency in a world of oppression. Voice becomes an act of resistance in the face of erasure and representation here is not just about being seen, but about being understood and valued.

Memory serves as a powerful tool for coping with trauma and preserving personal and collective history during times of war. In *A Thousand Splendid Suns*, memory helps characters endure years of violence and loss. Mariam, for example, carries painful memories of her illegitimate birth and abuse, but she also remembers moments of love and connection, especially with Laila. These memories shape her final act of sacrifice, giving her life meaning. While Laila, chooses to honor the past by returning to Kabul and building a girls' school as a symbol of hope and remembrance: "But, mostly, Mariam is in Laila's own heart, where she shines with the bursting radiance of a thousand suns" (Hosseini 414). This illustrates how Mariam remains present in Laila's heart, reflecting the importance of memory and loyalty in the face of historical trauma. Similarly, in *The Book Thief*, memory is portrayed through storytelling. Liesel writes her own book to document her life during Nazi Germany, preserving the memory of

her loved ones. Max also expresses his memories and fears by writing stories, turning memory into resistance. The novel ends with the haunting line: "I am haunted by humans" (Zusak 550). This sentence, spoken by Death at the end of the novel, captures the emotional weight of memory and trauma, emphasizing how even Death is deeply affected by the suffering of humanity during times of conflict. By highlighting memory as both painful and essential, the novels suggest that remembering is not just about the past but also, an act of survival, identity, and resistance. In both novels memory represents as a way of preserving identity after trauma. However, traumatized individuals use memory to understand their identity and make sense of suffering.

In conclusion, *A Thousand Splendid Suns* and *The Book Thief* demonstrate that war is a psychological trauma, not just a historical event. It reshapes identity, threatens childhood innocence, and silences voices. Through the use of postcolonial elements, the two novels show how marginalized individuals, especially women and children, deal with oppression and colonialism. However, despite the violence and loss, these characters persevere and resist to reclaim their rights and decide how to determine their fate. They do not lose faith that there is still hope behind this chaos. Despite the destruction and dehumanization, two novels show how memory, love, and storytelling can become powerful tools of resistance. In the end, one can find that war is not just about resistance but also about the unfinished struggles against the colonial history.

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